

ORDER OF PRINCIPLES OF SENTENCES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The article compares the order of sentences in Uzbek and English with the help of examples and tells how they change.

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When everyone is speaking, they pay attention not to the grammatical structure or word order of the sentence, but to the short and clear statement of the point they want to make. But the order of clauses is important in expressing an idea. In unnecessary cases, changing the positions of sentence parts can have a positive or negative effect on the meaning of the sentence, as a result, some additional meanings may appear in the sentence, or spelling and stylistic errors may occur. Therefore, it is appropriate to learn a foreign language in comparison with the mother tongue.

Uzbek and English both have five different clauses, and comparing the order of these clauses shows more differences than similarities. That's why many students face difficulties while translating. Word order in every language is based on fixed rules. Not everyone knows how to change the position of the parts of a sentence. Therefore, each language should follow its own grammatical rules when making a sentence. Let's compare the order of parts of sentences in Uzbek and English: in Uzbek, without exception, possessive always comes before the participle, and the participle comes at the end of the sentence. For example: Pirmuhammad Aziz tashrif buyurdi. Sen xuddi Muhammad Sultonga o'xshaysan.

In English: Pirmuhammad Aziz has visited. You look like Muhammad Sultan. A change in word order can also change grammatical meaning. This is as follows:

-If the adjective and the adjective change, the adjective becomes a possessor, the adjective becomes a participle, that is, the phrase becomes a sentence. For example: Go'zal Samarqand, Samarqand go'zal. In English, to turn a phrase into a sentence, it is necessary to use the verb to be in exchange of adjectives and adverbs.

- When possessive and participle are interchanged, possessive becomes participle and participle becomes possessive. For example: Yetti kun bir haft, bir hafta etti kun. This situation can also be observed in English. Seven days are a week. A week is seven days.

In Uzbek, the position of the participle in relation to the possessor is more strict, that is, it can often come at the end of the sentence. In some places, the possessive comes after the subject or participle. However, even then the possessive comes before the participle. For example: Tashqarida Ulug'bekni qurshab olib kelgan beku navkarlar qo'riqchilik qilmoqda(P. Kadirov). In English: The guards who brought Ulugbek surrounding him were guarding outside.

The following difference can be seen in the translation. In Uzbek, possessor comes after its determiner, while in English, possessor comes at the beginning of the sentence, and the determiner is followed by the interrogative pronoun who(kimki). If the possessive and determiner positions in this sentence are changed in English, both the grammatical structure and the meaning of the sentence will change. That is, the determiner becomes a special interrogative sentence and is not associated with either the possessor or the participle.

But in the Uzbek language: Tashqarida beku navkarlar Ulug'beklar qurshab olib kelganlar qo'riqchilik qilmoqda edi. In the Uzbek language, the logically stressed word goes before the participle and is pronounced with a stronger tone

than other words. In English, there is no change of place in this case, it is only pronounced with a strong tone.

The order of the participle with the possessive can change when the sentence is spoken in an exclamatory, command, or interrogative tone. For example: In exclamation: Yashasin ozodlik! ! (P. Kadyrov). In English: Live freedom!

In a commanding tone: Eshiting, dutorni qiyvoradi bu yigit. But this situation cannot be expressed in English. Interrogative tone: Yurtga yana soliq soldimi bu zolim podsho?

In English: Has this severe king taxed the country again? In English, if the participle contains an auxiliary or modal verb, the verbs listed come before the possessive and the main verb remains in place. Also, if the participle consists of the verb "to be", "to have", then a whole participle comes before the possessor. For example: Do you like these mysteries? Are these scientists in the lab?

In excerpts: "Bu tomonini o'ylamapmiz" - deb tan oldi Uvays Tarxon. In English: "We did not think about this side" - Admitted Tarkhan. Ne bir hujraki, kom topg'ay ko'ngil, Dame anga or topg'ay ko'ngil. Inversion also occurs when the sentence begins with the word "here"(mana). Here is my card. Here comes my brother John..

The complement comes between the possessive and the participle because it is attached to the participle in the sentence. For example: Inson har bir ishni mehr bilan qilmog'i lozim. Let's translate this sentence into English: a man should do every work by kind.

In Uzbek and in English, the determiner comes before the word that it has determined. If there are all three types of determiner in a sentence, it takes place as follows: demonstrative, adjective, explanatory determiner (possessive or complement). For example: Aziz onasining o'ng qo'lini avaylab kafilariga oldi.

Let's translate this sentence into English and compare the order of determiners in it.

For example: Aziz carefully took the right hand into his palms.

So, the order of determiners in English is similar to that in Uzbek, but if we give this sentence with the preposition "of", some changes occur. For example: Aziz carefully took the right hand of his mother into his palms.

Looking at the translation, in English the attributive determiner remains in place, but the demonstrative is placed after the determiner and the indefinite. That is, we should always pay great attention to the difference between experiences. Also, in English, most adjectives formed with the suffixes "able" and "ible" can come after nouns. For example: the only person visible. The most interesting thing imaginable. The case is always attached to the participle and in Uzbek comes before the participle. But place and time, sometimes purpose and reason can come at the beginning of the sentence. For example: Tevarak-atrofdan hanuzgacha jimjitlik hukm surmoqda (P. Kadyrov). Ertalab (when?) atayin (For what purpose?) sizni qidirib kelgan edim. Achinganidan (For what purpose?) uni afv etdi.

In English, the cases of place and time can come at the beginning or end of the sentence. Hol is similar to the Uzbek language. For example: On Tuesday night the new laundrymen arrived. Probably we will try tomorrow.

In conclusion, in English, it is often necessary to be careful with the use of adverbs. Because according to the rules of the English language, they come between the possessive and the participle or between the participle and the preposition. If the participle is formed from an intransitive verb, the accusative case follows the participle, if it is formed from a transitive verb, after the intransitive object, if it is formed from a transitive verb, after the object object comes later. For example: "You do not need to worry about me, Louise" said stoutly. And it should be mentioned that if the participle consists of a verb with a preposition, the cases of the participle and the preposition consist of an auxiliary, a

modal, the verb "to be" and the main verb, and the auxiliary and the main verb o comes between For example: She leaned lightly against his shoulder. Cases of degree-quantity always come before a participle: I entirely agree with you. If there are more than one case in English, when placing them, pay attention to the case of the place, first the small place, then kata placeholder is used. For example: I studied in a language school in England. In Uzbek, the opposite is true: Men Angliyadagi til maktabida o'qiganman. Comparing and analyzing the examples in Uzbek and English shows that there are similarities and differences in the order of sentence fragments in both languages. Knowing these differences makes it easier to translate accurately and completely from one language to another.

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